

A STUDY ON THE ROLE OF FINANCIAL LITERACY AMONG SMALL RETAIL BUSINESSMAN IN TUTICORIN

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Abstract

Financial literacy is crucial for individuals and businesses alike. It empowers individuals to make informed financial decisions, manage resources effectively, and achieve long-term financial stability. For small business owners, financial literacy is particularly important as it influences decision-making, business growth, and overall financial health. The proposed research aims to comprehensively understand the financial landscape of small retail business owners in Tuticorin. By examining the impact of financial education on decision-making, assessing the prevalence of banking practices, and evaluating the awareness and utilization of credit facilities, this study will contribute to a deeper understanding of the financial needs and challenges faced by this segment. Totally 40 responds were collected and analysed to test our hypothesis. Regression analysis and t-test is been made. It was found that the demographics of the respondents does not have association with their financial knowledge. This study helps to learn more about the importance of the role of financial literacy in the decision-making process of retailers.

Key Words: Financial Literacy, Retail Business, Credit Facility, Financial Awareness, Banking Practice.

INTRODUCTION

The capacity to comprehend and use a variety of financial abilities, such as investing, budgeting, and personal financial management, is known as financial literacy. People may increase their general well-being, create financial stability, and make wise financial decisions by becoming well-informed about money matter. Retail business owners need to be financially literate. It serves as their compass in the tangled realm of trade. A retailer who is financially literate can handle cash flow, comprehend financial documents, and decide on pricing, inventory, and spending with knowledge. It is vital to comprehend that market volatility is an inherent feature of the financial environment. Financial literacy is essential to the success of a retail business and goes beyond simple math. It gives merchants the ability to navigate the ever-changing retail world, allocate resources optimally, and make well-informed decisions. The sound financial management of retail enterprises is critical to their success and long-term viability. With Tuticorin district's distinct economic environment, financial literacy becomes even more important for small company owners. In order to better understand the critical role that financial literacy plays among Tuticorin district's retail business owners, this study will focus on the role of financial literacy among small retail business. Gaining insight into the importance of financial literacy will help us devise ways to improve small business owners' financial capacities and support the growth of Tuticorin's entrepreneurial sector.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Limited adoption of contemporary business methods and low financial literacy provide major obstacles for Tuticorin's small retail businesses. The real methods used by business owners clearly differ from the financial knowledge and abilities needed for effective retail operations. By examining the knowledge and use of accounting records, online banking, credit facilities, and tax compliance among small retail company owners in Tuticorin, this study seeks to determine the scope of this gap. The results will shed light on the particular financial difficulties that these businesses confront and help with the creation of focused actions that will improve both their financial standing and general performance.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

There have been many studies in the past that have been analysed. The current study entitled 'A Study on the Role of Financial Literacy Among Small Retail Businessman in Tuticorin' aims to find out the level of financial literacy prevailing in the current era that plays an important role in the improvement of this retail sector. This study helps retail business men to gain insights on

importance of financial literacy for the growth of their business. This study is conducted among small retail businessmen in Tuticorin Taluk.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Primary and Secondary method of data collection is used for the present study such as questionnaire and observation methods. All the information and the data are properly classified and arranged in tabular form.

Research Design

Data is collected through distributing questionnaire to retail businessman and the response were collected. This study is collected through primary data .

Sampling Design

Research methodology mainly focused on quantitative method and survey study considered as a research technique. The data collected are original in nature. It is the first hand information for the collection of information **(data) from 40 Respondents**. 10 Respondents are selected by convenience sampling method.

Collection of Data

The data required for the study have been obtained from primary and secondary data.

(a) Primary Data

To obtain data a well-structured questionnaire was prepared after analysing the various aspects of the topic and utmost care was given to ensure that the questions included suit to the purpose of the study and can easily be understood by the respondents to get the responses and feedback. In this study data were collected by distributing a questionnaire to the retail businessmen.

(b) Secondary Data

Secondary data includes information that already exists which has been collected from various journals, research papers, magazines, websites, reports and books. The collected data were recorded, coded, tabulated and analysed with the help of statistical tools. In this study secondary data were collected from various educational websites.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To assess the awareness and utilization of credit facilities among small business owners.
- 2) To measure the impact of financial education in the process of decision making of the retailers

3) To know the prevalence of banking practice among small business owners in Tuticorin.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Amit Pandey, Ravi Kiran, Rakesh Kumar Sharma (2022)¹ in the study titled “Investigating the Impact of Financial Inclusion Drivers, Financial Literacy and Financial Initiatives in Fostering Sustainable Growth in North India” aims to understand how financial inclusion (driven by digitalization, technology, and usage), financial literacy, and government initiatives contribute to sustainable growth in North India. Using PLS-SEM, the research found that financial inclusion positively impacts sustainable growth, and this effect is strengthened by financial literacy. Government initiatives also contribute positively. The study emphasizes the interconnectedness of these factors and the need for combined efforts to achieve sustainable development goals in the region.

Neha Ramnani Bhargava¹, Dr. Sachin Mittal, Dr. Vivek S. Kushwaha (2017)² in the study titled “Impact of Financial Literacy on Personal Financial Management Based on Occupation “ The purpose of this study is to analyse the impact of financial literacy on personal financial management with respect to different occupation groups in India. To conduct the study, analysis of variance (ANOVA) had been applied on a sample of 650 respondents out of which 296 were service class, 216 were business class and 138 were Self occupied professionals. The study found that financial literacy level, personal financial management skills and its impact differs significantly between Service class, Business class and Self occupied professionals in India. The study revealed that Service class and self-occupied occupation groups share good level of financial literacy and applies their learned concepts into their real life but business class individuals does not possess high level of financial literacy and thus have average personal financial management.

Sumit Agarwal and Et.al (2015)³ in the study titled “ Financial literacy and financial planning: Evidence from India “ typically aims to assess the level of financial knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours among individuals. This study employed quantitative methods, such as surveys, to gather data on financial literacy levels, investment patterns, debt management, and insurance coverage. The findings generally indicate a moderate level of financial literacy, with significant variations across demographic groups. While many respondents demonstrate basic understanding of financial concepts, deeper knowledge about investment planning and risk management is often lacking. The research highlights the need for improved financial education to enhance individuals' ability to make informed financial decisions and achieve long-term financial goals.

Sobhesh Kumar Agarwalla and Et.el (2013)⁴ in the study titled “ Financial literacy among working young in urban India” typically aims to assess the extent of financial knowledge, identify factors influencing financial behaviour, and examine the impact on overall financial well-being. To achieve this researcher employed quantitative methods, such as surveys, to gather data from a representative sample of young adults. Key findings generally revealed a concerning gap in financial literacy, with areas like investment and debt management showing particular weaknesses. Socio-demographic factors influence financial knowledge, and there's a strong correlation between financial literacy and positive financial behaviours. This study underscore the need for financial education programs to improve financial outcomes for young people.

Thilakam.C (2012)⁵ in the study titled ‘Financial Literacy Among Rural Masses in India’ tries to assess the financial literacy levels of rural India and identify factors influencing it. Researchers employed surveys and questionnaires targeting rural populations, gathering data on demographics, income, education, access to financial services, and financial knowledge. Statistical analysis is used to examine relationships between these variables and financial literacy. Studies typically include a representative sample of rural residents, considering factors like age, gender, occupation, and geographical location to ensure diversity. Generally, financial literacy in rural India is found to be low, with significant variations across regions and demographics. Education level, income, and access to financial institutions emerge as key determinants. Women often exhibit lower financial literacy compared to men. The studies highlight the need for targeted financial education programs to empower rural populations and improve their financial decision-making.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The data analysis phase will systematically examine the collected information to address the research objectives. Descriptive statistics will be employed to summarize the characteristics of the sample and key variables. The findings from these analyses will be presented in a clear and concise manner to provide insights into the financial behaviour of small retail business owners in Tuticorin.

DEMOGRAPHIC FACTOR WISE CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Type of Business	Grocery Shop	16	40
	Medical Shop	12	30
	General Stores	8	20
	Stationery Shop	4	10
Age	Above 40	25	62.5
	31 – 40	10	25
	21 – 30	5	12.5
Income	Less than 25,000	10	25
	25,001 – 50,000	20	50
	50,001 – 75,000	7	17.5
	75,001 – 1,00,000	3	7.5
Educational Qualification	SSLC/HSC	30	75
	Degree and Diploma	10	25
Type of card	Debit card	33	82.5
	Credit card	7	17.5
Types of Account	Current Account	26	65
	Savings Account	10	25
	Joint Account	4	10
Retailer use Internet Banking or Not	Yes	32	80
	No	8	20

Credit Facility avail by the retailer	Cash Credit	10	25
	Over Draft	20	50
	Short Term Loan	5	12.5
	Working Capital Finance	5	12.5
Objects of preparing Books of Accounts.	To record cash inflow or outflow	6	15
	To find out the Profit or Loss	25	62.5
	To know the financial position of the Business	6	15
	To make further decision	3	7.5
What are the problem faced by the retailer in preparing the books of accounts	Lack of Knowledge	25	62.5
	Technological upgradation of accounting system	15	37.5
GST is file by the Retailer or Not	Yes	15	37.5
	No	25	62.5

Interpretation

Thoothukudi retailers (N=40) predominantly run grocery stores (40%), are over 40 (62.5%), and earn between ₹25,001-50,000 (50%). Most have only SSLC/HSC education (75%) and use debit cards (82.5%) and current accounts (65%). Internet banking is widely adopted (80%), but credit card usage is low (17.5%). Overdrafts are the primary credit source (50%). Retailers mainly track profit/loss (62.5%) but struggle with accounting knowledge (62.5%) and technological upgrades (37.5%). A significant number don't file GST (62.5%). This suggests a need for financial literacy

and technology training, especially in accounting and GST compliance, to support these small businesses.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS TEST BETWEEN THE INCOME AND THE TYPE OF CREDIT FACILITY AVAILABLE TO RETAILERS

H_0 = There is no significant association between the income and the type of credit facility available to retailers

H_1 = There is a significant association between the income and the type of credit facility available to retailers

SUMMARY OUTPUT

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.895274
R Square	0.801515
Adjusted R Square	0.468182
Standard Error	5.635386
Observations	4

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	1	384.7273	384.727	12.1145	0.073554			
Residual	3	95.27273	31.7576					
Total	4	480						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	0	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
Credit	0.836364	0.240294	3.48059	0.04004	0.071642	1.60109	0.07164	1.60109

The regression model indicates a strong positive relationship between the variables. The model explains approximately 89.53% of the variation in type of credit of the retailers as indicated by the R-squared value of 0.895274. The coefficient for the independent variable is 0.836364, suggesting that for every one-unit increase in the independent variable, credit is predicted to increase by 0.836364 units. The positive relationship is statistically significant at the 5% level (p-value = 0.040038).

CHI-SQUARE TESTS BETWEEN THE TYPE OF BUSINESS AND THEIR FINANCIAL LITERACY

Test Statistic	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.234	3	0.435
Likelihood Ratio	1.453	3	0.228
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.234	1	0.267
No. of Valid Cases	40		

Crosstabulation Table (Observed & Expected Counts)

Type of Business	Observed Count	Expected Count
General Stores	8	8.0
Grocery Shop	16	16.0
Medical Shop	12	12.0
Stationery Shop	4	4.0

Interpretation

- Pearson Chi-Square value (2.234) with $df = 3$ and $p = 0.435$:
 - Since $p > 0.05$, we fail to reject the null hypothesis.
 - This means there is no significant association between business type and the number of respondents.
- Likelihood Ratio (1.453, $p = 0.228$):
 - Again, $p > 0.05$, confirming no statistical significance.
- Linear-by-Linear Association (1.234, $p = 0.267$):
 - No strong trend across categories.

Final Conclusion:

- The data suggests that the number of respondents across different business types is proportionate to expectations.
- Financial literacy levels among different business types are not significantly different in this sample.

SUMMARY AND DISCUSSIONS

The study delved into the financial landscape of small business owners in Tuticorin, focusing on the impact of financial education, banking practices, and credit facility utilization. Findings revealed there is no significant association between the demographics and other dependent variables in this study. These insights underscore the need for tailored financial interventions to address the specific challenges faced by small businesses in the region. A thorough strategy is necessary to improve financial literacy in the retail sector. Strong staff training programs should be put in place, including both industry-specific expertise like inventory management, cost control, as well as pricing tactics as well as basic financial principles like investing, saving, and budgeting. Adopting technology strategically may greatly improve financial literacy. Mobile apps can give retailers easy access to financial resources and resources for learning . The effect of financial literacy programs may be increased by establishing solid alliances with financial institutions, trade groups, and academic institutions. In the end, collaborations may help the retail industry as a whole by facilitating the exchange of resources, knowledge, and best practices.

By enhancing financial literacy, promoting accessible banking services, and expanding credit opportunities, it is possible to foster a more robust and resilient small business ecosystem in Tuticorin.

CONCLUSION

Financial literacy is a vital component for the sustained growth and success of retail businesses. Retailers that possess a solid understanding of financial concepts are more equipped to make well-informed decisions, allocate resources efficiently, and handle the intricacies of the market. Retailers may increase profitability, reduce risks, and create a robust company by comprehending financial accounts, managing cash flow well, and putting smart financial plans into practice. However, the retail environment is dynamic, marked by shifting consumer behaviors, innovations in technology, and economic fluctuations. In order to prosper in this context, retailers need to consistently improve their financial literacy. This entails using financial technology, keeping abreast of industry developments, and, if needed, obtaining expert advice.

The findings of this research can inform the development of targeted financial literacy programs, banking services, and credit products tailored to the specific requirements of small business owners in the region. The findings shows that there is a significant relationship between the demographics

and other variables in this study pertaining changes in demographics will leads to changes in the financial products usage of the retailers. It is the significant responsibility of our Tamil Nadu government to know making investments in financial literacy is not merely an option but an essential requirement for retail businesses sector. Retailers may position themselves for long-term success and add to the sector's overall economic vibrancy by making financial education and development a priority.

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